

1 **Learning to organize the collective will: Can horizontal practice provide an** 2 **alternative starting point for organization?**

3 **Abstract**

4 Mainstream organization theory takes the hierarchically structured and efficiency focused
5 business organization as its starting point. While alternatives exist, even these literatures take
6 the mainstream organization theory as their key reference. Alternatives therefore often remain
7 more reactionary than revolutionary. In the increasingly unstable world where strong calls for
8 change towards sustainable futures are put forward highlighting the need for collaboration, a
9 hierarchical starting point creates a dissonant, unsatisfactory reference point to understanding
10 what we call here the ‘organization of the collective will’. We illustrate how both hierarchical
11 and horizontal organization practice come with their own convictions, institutions and social
12 dynamics; yet, there is limited discussion at present as to what learning and maintaining
13 horizontal practice requires. In this paper, we study how we may imagine the normalization of
14 horizontality through learning to organize the collective will. We use two extended empirical
15 illustrations, one from a historical narrative of a pre-capitalist society and another drawing on
16 the experience of a pronouncedly post-capitalist community. We aim to show that to be viable,
17 learning to organize the collective will needs to interweave values and practices to a future
18 orientation. Our findings highlight what learning to think and work horizontally would mean
19 for contemporary organization theory and its underlying premises.

20 **Keywords:** Organization, collective will, horizontal practice, normalised horizontality,
21 learning, socialization

22 **Introduction**

23 The field of organization studies is built on the idea of hierarchy to the extent that hierarchical
24 relations have become synonymous with organization (Iannello, 1992; March and Simon,
25 1958; Thompson, 1967). While alternative forms of relating among equals can be observed in
26 associations (Blau and Scott, 1963), cooperatives (Helmberger and Hoos, 1962) or trade unions
27 (Warner, 1972), a standard definition of organization typically expressly excludes structures
28 other than hierarchical forms. “*An organization is a collectivity with a relatively identifiable*
29 *boundary, a normative order, **ranks of authority**, communications systems, and membership*
30 *coordinating systems...*” (Hall, 1991: 32, emphasis added). Thompson (1967) sees complex
31 organizations such as manufacturing firms, hospitals, schools, armies, and community agencies
32 as hierarchies with technical, managerial and institutional levels of responsibility and control,
33 and led by managers with discretionary powers. Ahrne and Brunsson (2019) even describe
34 hierarchy as equating to the authority structure of any collective: hierarchy is the structure
35 resulting from decisions on who can make decisions and what those decisions encompass. Even
36 critical studies of organization, including those examining alternative organizations or social
37 movements, start from the dominant mainstream form of the (commercial) organization and
38 often only replace formal hierarchies with informal ones (Rothschild-Whitt, 1979).

39 Why is this dominance of hierarchy problematic? From the perspective of alternatives, if any
40 alternative form of organization is theorized as a response to the contemporary dominant
41 capitalist form, this is a historical fallacy (Polanyi, 1944) and a reactionary rather than
42 revolutionary approach. Hierarchy has recently become a more fluid concept (Clegg and
43 Hardy, 1999); yet, in practice, most humans are socialized to accept hierarchical norms,
44 practices, and processes (Morgan, 2006) to the detriment of understanding the same aspects in
45 horizontality archetypes (Nunes, 2021), and to learning and cultivating horizontal practice (Fiol
46 and O’Connor, 2017a, 2017b). We question the legitimacy of the dominant social order vis-à-

47 vis the successes and failures of any alternative *collective will*. The concept of the collective
48 will aligns the discursive formulation of a course of collective action (Jacobsson, 1997) and its
49 prefigurative, future-oriented and inclusive organization (e.g. Laamanen, 2022; Schiller-
50 Merkens, 2022a). We argue that the relation between the two is a central dilemma around the
51 (de)normalization of hierarchy.

52 This article draws on the definition of organization as “*systems of continuous, purposive, goal-*
53 *oriented activity, involving two or more people, which exist within, and to some extent are*
54 *affected by, a value system provided by the larger societal environment*” (Iannello, 1992: 12).

55 We illustrate how learning to organize horizontally is essential to normalize horizontality as
56 the manifestation of collective will rather than hierarchy. The starting point is horizontal
57 practice of direct and ongoing (i.e. recursive) non-hierarchical decision-making (Nunes, 2021;
58 Sitrin, 2012). Horizontal practice accepts participants as autonomous agents with full
59 responsibility for organizing activities. The approach requires unlearning hierarchy within
60 spaces free of it (Mayo, 2020). Just as people are taught to surrender autonomy in hierarchical
61 practice, participants must learn how to maintain their autonomy in horizontal practice while
62 acknowledging that hierarchical practice may continue to intrude (e.g. Laamanen et al., 2019).

63 Two extreme empirical cases illustrate our approach to learning to organize the collective will,
64 which encourages participants to relate, learn skills, use resources, and act as part of a
65 horizontal organization practice. We highlight the demands horizontality places on participants
66 and how horizontal organization is not intrinsically familiar but must be actively cultivated.
67 Therefore, we illustrate key dimensions of horizontal practice within the process of learning
68 and enacting the *collective will* to establish *normalized horizontality*.

69 **From reactive and comparative to proactive and autonomous organization practice: can**
70 **horizontality be learned?**

71 The dominant hierarchical understanding holds that an organization's autonomy is granted by
72 external stakeholders and effectuated through organizational parameters (King et al., 2010).
73 Organizations limit their members' autonomy, forcing them to surrender at least some to
74 further organizational aims. *Hierarchical practice* relies on two presumptions: First, external
75 parties grant an organization authority and legitimacy, not members in the community. Second,
76 members accept top-down decision-making and accept the consequences of decisions made by
77 those higher up the hierarchy. This idea stretches back to Plato's notions on the state, which
78 included those in decision-making positions having superior knowledge and, thus, the right to
79 make decisions.

80 Both presumptions exclude the potential of horizontality. The idea and potential of *horizontal*
81 *practice*, which rests on the association of participants and the creation of their collective will,
82 becomes overwhelmed by the dominance of hierarchical discourse in organization studies and
83 socialization into hierarchical practice.

84 Recent organizational sociology argues for the need to restore the concept of organization in
85 organization studies (Ahrne et al., 2016, 2017; Ahrne and Brunsson, 2011, 2019; Apelt et al.,
86 2017). Yet, the tendency to consider hierarchy a legitimate, central, and defining element of
87 organization remains. Ahrne and Brunsson (2019) use the term hierarchy for decision-making
88 that does not draw on hierarchical structuring, but their work refers to how *decided* power is
89 distributed in "constitutions that alternatively or additionally stipulate that all organization
90 members can participate in decision-making, at least about some issues" (p. 13). Similarly,
91 drawing on Lukes (2005), Kummelstedt (2022) juxtaposes directive, procedural, and discursive
92 power in hierarchical and collective forms of leadership, pointing to the individual and
93 collective power of giving orders, regulating procedures and outcomes, and controlling the

94 legitimacy and desirability of action. Kummelstedt thus implies the presence of horizontality
95 in organization studies, and horizontality has infiltrated discussions on work organization
96 (Barker, 1993; Kokkinidis, 2015; van der Vegt et al., 2010), associations (Ahrne and Brunsson,
97 2008; Berkowitz and Bor, 2018; Lawton and Rajwani, 2018), collaboration (Austin and
98 Seitanidi, 2014a, 2014b; Gray, 1989; Gray et al., 2022; Gray and Purdy, 2018), social
99 movements (Järvi et al., 2018; Laamanen, 2022; Schiller-Merkens, 2022b; Simsa and Totter,
100 2017), and leadership (Uhl-Bien, 2011). Horizontality features in work on introducing
101 democratic practices, particularly within alternative organizations (Parker et al., 2014).
102 Horizontal practice varies widely between interest, ownership, and grassroots orientations and
103 also more or less formal groups (e.g. associations, collectively-managed companies,
104 cooperatives, foundations, or activist groups). For instance, in alternative democratic
105 organization models, ownership, participant rights, and social contracts are connected to
106 inclusive interaction and institutions (e.g. Diefenbach, 2020; Dixon, 2014).

107 Accordingly, while it has been established that organization can be horizontal and hierarchical
108 practice is not a prerequisite, much of the literature on horizontal organization identifies
109 people's unfamiliarity with horizontal ways of thinking and acting and the tendency to revert
110 to hierarchical solutions as a hindering factor (e.g. Laamanen et al., 2019). Participants
111 unfamiliar with horizontal practices may intentionally or unintentionally undermine the
112 organization by assuming a position of authority and expecting others to serve. Additionally,
113 participants might reject the responsibility of self-governance, preferring others to govern.
114 Consequently, dominant, hierarchical forms of organizing practice and situating ourselves in
115 them are accepted as immutable (Battilana, 2006; Morgan, 2006).

116 Socialization to (existing) collective structures, beliefs, and ways of doing are central to
117 theories of social practice (Reckwitz, 2002; Schatzki, 2006). These view the social world as
118 constructed through shared practices that represent *knowledgeable collective action* (Barnes,

119 2001; Gherardi, 2010, 2012; Orlikowski, 2010). Shared ideas and ideals are reproduced by
120 practitioners who accept and engage in the focal practice. However, as collective action,
121 practice transcends the individual. Over time, practices form, configure, and change in
122 synthesis with the 1) (un)subscription of practitioners to the practice; 2) integration of
123 knowledge (as know-how), meaning (conventions and rules) and materials (resources), and
124 changes in institutions and environments (contexts) (Forno et al., 2022; Shove et al., 2012;
125 Shove and Pantzar, 2007). Moreover, practices are teleoaffective formations (Welch, 2020)
126 and thereby future-oriented to motivate people in the pursuance of end goals. As an
127 organizational phenomenon, practices concern everyday organizational activities and their
128 outcomes. They illustrate routine (habitual) performances that construct, produce, reproduce
129 and change the structural features of the social over time (Whittington and Vaara, 2012).

130 Aligning practice with value systems encourages granting access, respect, and recognition in a
131 social setting. Participation becomes a function of individuals' aspiration for group
132 membership and alignment with the nature of the demands of participation, that is, learning the
133 practice. Even loosely formulated communities include some recognition of participation in
134 lieu of formal membership (e.g. Ahrne and Brunsson, 2011; de Bakker et al., 2017). However,
135 the notion that a horizontal organization requires a different mindset to emerge from
136 (re)socialization to *collaborative* learning (Blee, 2012) remains unexplored. Polletta (2002: 11)
137 illustrates *why* participatory democracy in horizontal decision-making leads to learning to
138 foster effective action. Where hierarchical rule and decision-making is opaque, "participatory
139 deliberation yields citizens who are more knowledgeable, public-spirited, better able to see the
140 connections between their own interests and those of others, and more willing to re-evaluate
141 their own interest". Polletta also points out that participation in decision-making increases
142 ownership and "the pleasures of learning that sustain people's participation" (2002: 74).

143 A horizontal practice is learned with (and from) peers, and through creating and claiming free
144 spaces and allowing people to learn (via formal education institutions or otherwise) can make
145 the horizontal organization function (e.g. Mayo, 2020). The formation of a collective will can
146 be considered a discursive process, the “continual praxis of citizens in framing a collective
147 course of action” (Jacobsson, 1997: 70) that justifies, rather than sets, an organizational form
148 for democracy. Alternatively, DeHaven-Smith (1998) claims that mass publics lack form and
149 direction without a discursive collective will; when organized, the collective will shapes the
150 political institutions through which it is channelled (Hardt and Negri, 2004). Collective will is
151 formed through negotiation and deliberation, shaping and reshaping, learning and unlearning
152 (Fiol and O’Connor, 2017a, 2017b; Jacobsson, 1997). Learning how to collectively channel
153 the collective will in horizontal practice starts with viewing participants as autonomous agents
154 with a full understanding of and responsibility for organizing action.

155 However, socialization to horizontal practice is neither complete nor pure. Laamanen et al.
156 (2020) illustrate how hierarchical and horizontal practices are often blended, meaning that
157 organizing reacts to the composition of the participants and their (non-)hierarchical mindsets.
158 Similarly, Polletta (2002) sees a solution to formality and openness in a compromise where
159 rules *and* relationships are instituted for accountability (e.g. non-forceful decision-making),
160 trust and respect. Without relationality, hierarchies become rigid, and learning will suffer. Blee
161 (2012) claims that *collective* learning, or learning to organize together, withers without
162 acknowledgement, and organizing becomes something done for others (see Piven and Cloward,
163 1979) and what could be termed the constitutionalization of the collective will fails when only
164 some participants remain decision-makers (Graham and Papadopoulos, 2021). Our empirical
165 illustration of two cases of learning to organize drawn from contexts outside the dominant
166 capitalist system hierarchical model (and its imperialism of minds and spaces; Brand and
167 Wissen, 2021). This resonates with Clegg et al. (2005) who view organization as “a constant

168 state of becoming” (p. 158). We consider relationality and learning collective practice foster
169 the emergence of processes with horizontal aims and outcomes.

170 **Methodology**

171 Our examination unites two existing sets of data on pre- and post-capitalist communities that
172 reveal commonalities and highlight in learning to organize the collective will. We aim to
173 provide a nuanced theorization of the practices of learning horizontal organization practice.
174 The cases differ significantly but correspond in terms of horizontal ideals of community
175 building and maintenance, and thus constitute an extreme case (Patton, 2002).

176 *The Nhunggarra case*

177 The Nhunggarra is a First People community in Australia once located on the fertile riverine
178 plain in current New South Wales. The tribe spanned 26 interconnected communities until the
179 British occupation in the early nineteenth century: 90% of the Nhunggarra were killed
180 directly by the settlers or diseases they introduced, today only a handful remains. In 1788, the
181 Nhunggarra was estimated at around 500 to 1000 people per community and between 15,000
182 and 25,000 people across the 26 communities, forming the Community of Communities (CoC)
183 (Sveiby and Skuthorpe, 2006). The CoC defied modern-day classification: it was all-embracing
184 and covered the lifespans of the individual members but ensured no elite benefitted more than
185 another. It was not a formal entity because authority was not a legitimate permanent structure
186 at CoC level. Anthropologists call it a cultural bloc, which reflects kinship relations and
187 similarities of languages and belief systems but not organizational practices. The CoC
188 comprised local collectives responsible for specific areas of knowledge that only met when
189 summoned and only in exceptional cases convened as the whole CoC. The same individuals
190 influenced consensual decisions on home community and CoC levels with a quasi-bottom-up
191 authority. The community data are ten orally conveyed law stories memorized by the elders,

192 mainly recounted by their custodian, Tex Skuthorpe. The law stories are a unique time capsule
193 of empirical data portraying the situation in 1788, before the calamity of British colonization.
194 Aboriginal law is not a legal framework in the Western sense: the law stories encapsulate
195 spiritual knowledge, cosmology, social behaviour rules, guidelines for behaviour around birth
196 and death, relationships with animals, land management, sacred places, and diplomatic
197 relations with neighbouring communities. The authority of the law stories derived from an
198 ancestor from the time of creation, making it indisputable. The Nhunggabarra thus had a moral
199 code of conduct on three levels: individual, home country, and the level of the 26 communities¹.
200 Transgressions carried both social sanctions and penalties. While the code was not law in the
201 Western sense, it probably influenced individuals' minds and behaviours more
202 comprehensively than do modern legal systems.

203 *The STAP case*

204 Stadin Aikapankki (STAP or the Helsinki Timebank) is an alternative exchange network in
205 Helsinki (Finland). The community is the largest timebank in the country and has operated
206 since 2009. STAP has over 4,000 members, who have exchanged roughly 39,000 hours in the
207 past 12 years. The overall aim of STAP is to build an inclusive community to counter the
208 economic and social conflict emanating from the capitalist relations of the market economy.
209 Any economic value created through community work and consumption remain within the
210 community. While not a formal organization, STAP sometimes assembles for meetings and
211 events and individual members meet to conduct exchanges. This illustrates the two particular
212 domains: the exchange domain and the community building domain. The community
213 organizing principles rest on the creation of inclusive, transparent and noncoercive social
214 relations (Laamanen, 2022) with a low joining threshold and include activities beyond
215 exchanges. Members' conduct in the community is guided by a set of values and quasi-

216 directives. Contemporary social movement communities like STAP share challenges, such as
217 issues around the availability of participants and the actions they are willing to undertake (e.g.,
218 offering material or moral support or even risking their lives or livelihoods in protest action or
219 strikes; e.g. Klandermans, 2004). Because STAP is an ongoing community project, the
220 narrative here draws on participatory research engagement in the community. The insights
221 presented are based on documents, exchange records, participant observation, and interviews
222 with activists conducted by the second author since 2015.

223 **Learning to organize the collective will**

224 The case analysis followed an explorative design developing an iterative, quasi-abductive
225 procedure. First, we reviewed key aspects of existing theories of hierarchical and horizontal
226 organization and then explored the practice of learning to organize the collective will. We then
227 reviewed the major differences between our cases to discover how communities following the
228 same principles of horizontality adopt highly divergent practices. Below, we present our
229 findings on what binds the communities and how they practice horizontality. We analyse the
230 path of individuals entering, operating in and exiting the collectives as domains with a specific
231 collective will.

232 *Entering the collective: learning to organize the collective will*

233 For the Nhunggabarra, the only possible route into the collective was by birth. However, the
234 process of entering the collective started before birth. The women's marriage law collective
235 covering the whole CoC decided which combination of kinship relations and totems fitted a
236 marrying couple. A new-born child assumed Nhunggal identity and was allocated its adult role
237 in the local community.

238 Learning to organize the collective will began with primary socialization in the family and
 239 continued at frequent *corroborees* (teaching events for the young) where law stories were
 240 conveyed through music, dance, and theatre. Initiated adults played the role of totem animals
 241 – who behaved disrespectfully and were subject to ridicule – to illustrate the wisdom of
 242 following the prescribed behaviours in the stories. However, some knowledge contained in the
 243 law stories could be abused and was restricted to initiated adults trusted to respect it.
 244 Knowledge was, therefore, coded at three levels. For the children, the first level might explain
 245 why crows are black and why cranes have a rasping call. The second level prescribed how to
 246 behave respectfully in the home community and was aimed at older children and adults. The
 247 third level addressed only adults and concerned how to behave respectfully to the other
 248 communities in the CoC.

249 *Table 1 An example from the Crane and Crow story (Sveiby, 2009).*

Narrative (Sveiby 2009)	Level	Behaviour Moral code
<i>The expert fisherman Crane is pulling up lots of fish from the river.</i>	3 Crane is jeopardising the breeding stock for the communities downstream.	<i>Do not catch more fish than you need.</i>
<i>Crow approaches and asks for a fish, but Crane demands that Crow must cook it.</i>	2 Crow should be free to prepare his own food	<i>Respect the views and integrity of other people.</i>

250

251 Tex's totem animal was the sand goanna (a lizard). The relationship was initiated via
 252 socialization (Sveiby, 2022) and began in childhood. Tex was sent out in the bush by the elders
 253 to complete tasks, which gradually became more difficult. He learned about goannas' family
 254 life, parenthood, birth and death, and how they acquired food. When he returned, he was asked
 255 to describe what he had learned and what it meant for him. The elders never criticized but might
 256 direct him to seek a clearer understanding. He knew he had passed one test when assigned

257 another more difficult task. This unimposing education taught him how to behave respectfully
258 toward his totem. Traditionally, he should next have become a journeyman.

259 Learning the codes of horizontal intercommunal relating for young men took considerable time.
260 Law stories portray some male ancestors as irresponsible, aggressive, and responsible for most
261 mistakes. Hence, the men needed extra training and experience in horizontal relations to
262 become responsible members of society. Every Nhunggal boy becomes a journeyman during
263 puberty. He must be socialized into each of the communities' values and learn how to behave
264 respectfully in the whole CoC. When he returned after some 18 years, he faced further initiation
265 ceremonies and an examination by a panel of wiringins (shamans) before he was considered
266 an independent adult who could marry and take on his responsibilities in the home community.
267 For young women, learning the codes of conduct began in puberty as they fulfilled their
268 community responsibilities, learning childcare and land management from married women.
269 Girls' education continued after marriage through association with the women of the husband's
270 community. This was connected to maternal responsibilities and her role as custodian for all
271 the lands of the CoC, a major responsibility given the land produced some 80% of the food
272 (Sveiby, 2011).

273 Being a contemporary urban community, membership in STAP is not regulated by kinship.
274 Timebanking typically provides a community service focused on local contexts,
275 neighbourhoods, and regions. Initially, STAP advocated local self-organized chapters but has
276 subsequently grown to cover the whole Helsinki metropolitan area. Membership is open to
277 anyone in the Greater Helsinki area, and the dynamics of exchange are determined by the local
278 members and their willingness to travel to conduct exchanges. The joining process is the most
279 formal one in the STAP community, involving registering via the community website. Every
280 new member is asked to agree to the community values and principles – the community ABC

281 (their rulebook) and exchange etiquette, which illustrate the community's values and aims both
282 locally and more globally.

283 The exchange process follows general timebanking principles (applicable to all timebanks) and
284 community principles (specific to STAP). The central tenet is that the skills any participant
285 offers are considered of equal value. Exchanges should be multilateral; that is, the members
286 engage with one another in different constellations and avoid forming exclusive trading
287 relationships. The participants are encouraged to keep transacting to keep the community
288 currency and work flowing. New members receive instructions on how to record hours
289 rendered or received, either via email or the website, but these practices are also discussed
290 during (monthly) meetings. Exchanges are recorded in an electronic ledger, an open-access
291 document on a global platform for community currency groups. Information on the platform is
292 transparent, and all members can review account balances to see how communal reciprocity is
293 working (or that value is not being hoarded). Investigations of members' practices are rare; on
294 occasion, the membership meeting discusses large surpluses and deficits but usually takes no
295 punitive action.

296 The direct democracy and prefigurative organizing at the heart of STAP often runs counter to
297 participants' experience of Finnish associational life with its clearly structured responsibilities.
298 In STAP, however, there is no formal induction but people joining are expected to accept the
299 focus and alternative ideals of the community. There are typical points of conflict for two
300 specific domains: one of immediate assistance in the everyday and another of building a larger
301 alternative economy. Specific STAP principles (that draw on more general timebanking
302 principles) aim to mitigate conflict emanating from participants' inherent socialization of and
303 experience in the market economy. Arguments typically relate to the quality of exchanges and
304 here the preferred method to arbitrate exchange disagreements is a conciliatory meeting
305 between the parties and the aim is that no solution is imposed on the parties. On the community

306 level, common problems in meetings include community principles and some participants
307 became frustrated with the socialization process for new members, feeling it diminished the
308 continuity of community's aims².

309 *Life in the collective: maintaining the collective will*

310 In the Nhunggal case, maintaining the collective will involves socialization by working in
311 collectives and participating in the corroborees. The children were socialized into the local
312 community's habits from birth. However, all newly-wed women and all men under 30 who
313 were on their learning journey across the CoC, originated from other communities within the
314 CoC; they thus spoke different, albeit related, languages and needed to be socialized into the
315 community's specific practices when they arrived. Also, the man who finally return to their
316 home community from their learning journey, needed to be socialized into the habits of the
317 new collectives they became a full member of in their home community.

318 All adults were members of several collectives. Perhaps the totem collective was closest to the
319 heart because a person joined that at birth. For example, the sand-goanna collective consists of
320 all the sand-goanna totem people in Australia. A person considered everyone who shared their
321 totem animal kin, and Tex spoke of relatives in every corner of Australia. On a journey, Tex
322 would just ask for the sand goannas and be welcomed as a son by the eldest sand-goanna couple
323 and as a brother by the other sand-goanna people, an experience shared by all journeying men
324 (Sveiby and Skuthorpe, 2006). There were between 35 and 50 local totem collectives (of
325 between 10 and 20 people) where the young learned conventions from the initiated adults
326 (Sveiby, 2022). In addition to these totem collectives, there were many other collectives for
327 e.g. hunting, exchange of goods with other communities, fishing, etc.

328 Maintaining the collective will across generations and communities required a horizontal
329 structure independent of individual positions of power. This was quite a challenge for primitive

330 people with egalitarian values who relied on an oral tradition. The solution was the *collectives*
331 *of collectives* that convened only in times of crisis. For example, if the sand goannas
332 disappeared from an area, the local sand goanna collective would perform ceremonies to
333 understand when they had disrespected the knowledge and confront themselves with their
334 mistakes. They would also alert the sand-goanna collectives in the other communities to
335 support the search for the cause of the problem. If there was no consensus on the cause of the
336 problem or the action required by the law, the local sand-goanna collective summoned all the
337 people of the CoC with a sand goanna totem— a collective of collectives – to reach a decision.
338 Tex witnessed how the marriage law collective solved such a problem in the 1960s at the CoC
339 level.

340 *Tex: A young bloke married a woman of the same totem. This was unheard of and*
341 *a serious break of the law and carried the death penalty. A call went out to all*
342 *women looking after marriage law, and they arrived from as far as Queensland.*
343 *They sat down and talked for a couple of weeks to reach a decision. In the end, the*
344 *women decided not to punish the couple because they agreed that they had to also*
345 *consider the white people's law. No men were involved in the matter (Sveiby and*
346 *Skuthorpe, 2006: 134).*

347 Two things are remarkable here, apart from the severity of the penalty. The strength of the CoC
348 structure, despite 150 years of occupation, and that the women could reach a consensus.
349 Imposing a death penalty in Australia would amount to murder: however, the CoC found a
350 horizontal way to maintain the collective will while still obeying the new law. The solution
351 was probably possible because the women were elders³. Moreover, the CoC had a rather
352 sophisticated institution to maintain the integrity of their law stories across generations – the
353 *tuckandee*. All adults had a personal tuckandee in another community who learned the same
354 knowledge and functioned as the “back-up copy” for the other person. Traditionally, Tex being

355 the custodian of the law stories, would have had a tuckandee learning the law stories of the
356 Nhunggabarra, and he would have been the tuckandee of a custodian in yet another community,
357 learning their law stories. This system of tuckandees was maintained by the women's network
358 between the communities.

359 In STAP, maintaining the collective will is less codified. Like other community groups
360 promoting complementary currencies, STAP seeks to create a parallel alternative economy and
361 marketplace. Alternative economy organizations offer a pertinent scene of experimentation
362 relating to localized autonomy, communal work, equal distribution, and multilateral reciprocity
363 (see e.g. Parker et al., 2014). The underlying timebanking and community principles reflect
364 these ambitions; however, several instances of organizing illustrate the collective will. Being
365 part of the community confers an individual moral obligation to participate in its activities.
366 While ideologically supportive, non-practising members swell the overall numbers of the
367 group, active participation (as opposed to idea patronage) is considered imperative to create an
368 alternative social order (Laamanen, 2022). Compelling participation goes against the ideals of
369 the community, but at the same time, the obligation to participate is in place to restrain any
370 formal authority from forming. This is a challenge, as the following quote from a meeting
371 memorandum (17 March 2013) illustrates:

372 *Since STAP is not a registered association, there has been no need for a formal*
373 *board or similar. The idea has also been to promote horizontal and direct*
374 *democracy, where responsibility is shared...In practice, it is challenging...efforts*
375 *will continue to be devoted to tasks without a board and more so that any STAP*
376 *member can participate in the activities, also flexibly in accordance with their*
377 *own life situation...It was noted that in the future task sharing, information flow*
378 *and decision-making must be communicated better than currently and more*
379 *organization is needed.*

380 The STAP community has repeatedly rejected any formal structure, the members believing it
381 antithetical to how the community *wants* to operate (Laamanen et al., 2019). There is an
382 inherent difficulty associated with inclusive action in an open, self-organizing form that STAP
383 has experimented with over the years. Attending to collective tasks (work in the community)
384 is based on the principles of *stigmergy* and *adhocracy* (Laamanen et al., 2019). Stigmergy is
385 work being distributed through self-organization as members sign up to undertake tasks that
386 must be completed. Adhocracy is flexible and situational decision-making, to allow for
387 maximum participation and minimum specification of authority. An online electronic
388 workspace and email list facilitate stigmergy. The tasks and responsibilities are communicated
389 via the universally accessible workspace. Transparency should support the drive to engage in
390 activities. All members are invited to undertake tasks (stigmergy), and there are working groups
391 with a list of tasks participants could allocate themselves to. Nevertheless, many members rely
392 on the founders and/or core activists for direction.

393 Membership meetings can resolve collective issues but are not considered representative of the
394 community's collective will, as one activist stated: "*Neither our meetings nor the core group*
395 *have ever been representative...of the entire membership or legitimized by anyone in*
396 *particular. We have not chosen any representatives. People [represent] themselves.*"
397 (Laamanen et al., 2019: 302). All members are invited to participate in the discussion and any
398 decisions are based on consensus among those present and reported to all members via
399 memoranda. Accordingly, decisions reflect the collective will of the situation. The authority to
400 decide (or impose a will on the collective) at the membership meeting is transitory because
401 members can subsequently reverse any decision in another meeting.

402 Stigmergic and adhocratic ideas are not inherent to the collective. These ideas are the
403 ideological background of certain active participants who orchestrate decisions and in part,
404 imported from other activist groups, such as the Finnish Social Forum, European Social Forum,

405 European Commons Assembly, the World Social Forum and the Degrowth networks. Tensions
406 sometimes emerge, particularly in relation to implicit legitimacy; then the community will
407 discuss the principles of activities, often calling for a clearer association structure. The STAP
408 activists strive to remain true to the initiative's ideals and manage the responsibility to progress
409 change while ensuring decision-making remains open, goals that are hindered by limited
410 participation among members. Nevertheless, there is pressure to hold meetings, record
411 discussions, and advance collaboration to move things forward. Leadership resembles an
412 aggregation of individual stigmergic acts and collective decisions made at membership
413 meetings.

414 Nevertheless, political steering may not represent the political convictions and identity
415 expressions behind the participants' everyday exchanges in the network. As one participant
416 highlighted: *"The point behind the timebank is that, although it is a political project, it is*
417 *concretized through these [everyday] exchanges. Then, I suppose, plenty of people don't find*
418 *this kind of [political] discussion interesting"*.

419 ***Exiting the collective: abandoning the collective will***

420 In the Nhunggal case, exiting the collective was normally occasioned by death. People were
421 not afraid of dying because it meant the end of earthly responsibilities. Eternal rewards were
422 secured by the women's mourning-ceremony collective performing ceremonies to guide the
423 spirit to the ancestors' campfires represented by the stars. Individuals could also leave the
424 village, which was not prohibited but was considered disrespectful. Adults knew how to survive
425 in the bush but might face roaming endlessly on Earth after death if the community did not
426 perform the appropriate mourning ceremonies. Demons featuring in some stories were believed
427 to be such spirits. Exiting by execution (performed by the wiringin) was possible but probably
428 more readily accepted than we might think today. A person repenting an offence was

429 guaranteed the mourning ceremonies. Emigration was not an option because it was impossible
430 to change the inherent Nhunggal identity, and none of the other communities would accept
431 such a person as a member.

432 For STAP members, exiting the collective is as simple as entering. Over the years, the size of
433 the community has remained steady, but numbers of exchanges have decreased significantly.
434 That might indicate the community lacks a strong collective moral reference point owing to
435 diminishing participation in common activities (such as membership meetings or organizing
436 rallies) and the vesting (or imposing) of authority on a few well-networked activists. The
437 situation raises the question of whether collective learning will be successful when left to
438 individuals; people should choose to work on issues they care about in a stigmergic, adhocatic
439 manner. When the workload falls on a few, most active participants (at some point) question
440 their participation. Laamanen et al. (2019) report a core member stating:

441 *“All last spring, I did nothing; nor did anyone else. And so that conversation [on*
442 *organization] was just discarded. And then I justified [my non-involvement], as I*
443 *had to finish my dissertation, but also to see what would happen if I retreated.*
444 *Whether someone takes that space... I said to [another founding member] in one*
445 *message: ‘What if we both just quit? Would it not be inclusive when we would say,*
446 *hey, if you complain that we use too much power, use it yourselves? Now, take it*
447 *and occupy it, like that.’ And I must have written a message that I would be*
448 *moving to the sidelines and hope that somebody else would take [centre stage].”*

449 The stories of the two communities above reflect the perspective of the individual participant
450 invited to enact horizontality. The two stories illustrate the underlying key dimensions of
451 horizontal practice within the process of learning and enacting the collective will that
452 eventually normalizes horizontality, if it doesn’t lead to abandonment.

453 **The conceptual dimensions of horizontality**

454 From the analysis of the two cases, we as presented in the previous section we have gotten an
455 understanding of the learning process, that is how may we learn the practice of horizontality,
456 how may we learn to organize the collective will. In this process, we also identified four
457 underlying dimensions of horizontality. The horizontal practice relies on a different set of
458 higher-order values which support the maintaining of the collective will. Horizontal practice
459 also relies on authority without positional leaders. Furthermore, decision-making in horizontal
460 practice relies on consensus. And finally, we highlight that in horizontal practice legitimacy
461 ought to come from within, from its members. These four dimensions are presented in little
462 more detail below.

463 The first conceptual dimension of horizontality is that of a set of *higher-order values* including
464 inclusiveness and mutual respect. Horizontal practice values inclusiveness and fosters an
465 environment facilitating everyone participating; the moral imperative is active collective
466 participation. Mutual respect in inclusion recognizes the dignity and value of every human
467 being and urges participants to recognize and respect the right of each person to be involved in
468 decisions that affect their life (Straus, 2002). Consensus decision-making often highlights full
469 participation, mutual understanding, inclusive solutions, and shared responsibility (Kaner,
470 2014). Participants are expected to be decision-makers and all are encouraged and empowered
471 to speak (Diefenbach, 2020; Haug, 2013) and be heard. Horizontal practice demands the ability
472 to empathize with others' viewpoints.

473 Respect is a central value in the Nhunggal society, respect not in the sense of obedience to
474 higher authority or admiration, but in the deep sense of acting from and seeing the integrity of
475 oneself and of others, knowledge and reflexivity are highly valued as they help to increase the
476 understanding of integrity (see also Sveiby, 2011). Respect therefore can play a central role in
477 explaining how people should relate to one another in horizontal organizing. The STAP

478 community is driven by a moral imperative to participate, to be a genuine member. This
479 imperative is codified into timebanking and specific STAP principles and mobilized during
480 interactions. Inclusive solutions connect to the idea that one should not only listen to the
481 quickest and loudest but also to the silent, the slow, and those struggling to express themselves
482 (Graeber, 2002). Collectively shared authority and responsibility restrains formal leadership
483 from exploiting control (Graeber, 2002; Laamanen et al., 2020) but also heighten expectations
484 related to the participation in communal decision-making. Even if horizontality is established
485 and maintained through collective decisions, reaching consensus relies on adhering to the key
486 principles.

487 The second conceptual dimension of horizontality is that of *authority without positional*
488 *leaders*. The basic starting point of hierarchical relating is positional authority whereas
489 horizontal practice relies on authority without leaders in office, aiming to equalize relations
490 and reject authority vested in one person. Authority is considered something produced in
491 interaction by the collective, thus the collective is responsible for counterbalancing positional
492 and knowledge-based authority by fostering open debate (Leach, 2013) and contesting
493 knowledge (Turnhout et al., 2020). Authority without positional leaders coincides with
494 leadership theory transitioning from a leader-follower focus to re-envisioning *the what* as a
495 social process occurring through human interactions. The focus shift to how the interactions
496 and skills required for collective learning and non-authoritative leadership emerge from among
497 multiple attributes (shared, distributed, collective and collaborative). However, studies are
498 empirically grounded in existing organizational practices and commercial organizations,
499 thereby assuming an existing hierarchical organizational structure with the leadership either
500 shared or distributed among individual managers or executives. Horizontal leadership is
501 illustrated in a process, project, or subgroup embedded within a hierarchical organization: here,
502 horizontality is ephemeral, as it is sometimes distributed and inclusive and sometimes

503 represents a hidden hierarchy (Empson, 2020). Uhl-Bien (2011) offered a more radical
504 proposition via the concept of relational leadership – leadership produced through relational
505 interactions. This approach theoretically enables horizontal leadership without appointed
506 leaders: the assumption is that leadership emerges in action from individuals’ interconnected
507 actions, which implies that the meanings of activities and goals are continuously being framed
508 and reframed for different contexts. Authority then is always situational and derives from
509 having knowledge useful in a particular situation, though as highlighted in the first dimension,
510 this authority comes with the need to respect the integrity of all involved.

511 The third conceptual dimension of horizontality is *consensus decision-making* when members
512 assume responsibility for making and implementing decisions. Accordingly, assenting to a
513 decision equates to committing to that decision. Horizontality relies on a collective consensus-
514 building process (see e.g. Susskind et al., 1999), whereby those people who are in some way
515 affected by a decision are involved in the process. The starting point for consensus-building
516 lies in higher-order value of respect. Respect for oneself means that each member participates
517 with integrity and takes full responsibility for the collective decisions made. While respect for
518 others means that members cannot impose a decision on another member, they respect the
519 integrity of others as this is needed for them to take full responsibility for collective decisions
520 made. When consensus arises on an issue, each member thus takes the responsibility for such
521 decision, and for following such decision. The Nhunggabarra and each of the 26 communities
522 rely on consensus decision-making. Decisions do not become set in stone, however, they can
523 in subsequent meetings be overturned or changed as members raise issues that were not
524 considered, or when a situation has changed and asks for adjustments. In STAP where not all
525 members participate, members are using consensus decision-making, though with different
526 members present at different times, consensus arises from more of a continuing adjusting
527 process, whereby those present can make proactive decisions on progressing issues, but these

528 decisions can be questioned by people, initiating a new decision process. Though, for STAP
529 members there always exists a real option of exit instead of raising issues of concern, which
530 can weaken its horizontality.

531 In contrast, hierarchical decision-making systems allow some individuals to evade
532 responsibility for decisions (Scott and Flanigan, 1996). The strong socialization to a
533 contemporary formalized organizational culture and organization of capitalism represents the
534 kind of environmental value system that influences the socialization to a collective will. In
535 STAP, some of the passive tendencies of the membership can reasonably be explained with the
536 kind of normalized hierarchy coming from a strong associational culture where interests are
537 represented but not necessarily mobilized. In contrast, when all members determine issues
538 affecting their life, consensus binds them to their decisions. Much of the research on consensual
539 decision-making addresses the challenges of making such processes work (Butler and
540 Rothstein, 1987; Dressler, 2006; Scott and Flanigan, 1996). Division of tasks is possible:
541 participants can accept tasks and make choices related to them; however, when actions affect
542 others, decisions must be made collectively. The process of collective decision-making aligns
543 participants with one another and a collective agenda, that is, the collective will.

544 The fourth and final dimension of horizontality we identified is *legitimacy*. An organization
545 (and the collective will) is maintained by its participants who establish and recognize it.
546 Nevertheless, as is highlighted in organization studies, legitimacy is also an issue of external
547 recognition and influence (King et al., 2010). Any organization, however horizontality
548 oriented, may need to address an external threat to legitimacy. Being recognized as a group can
549 legitimize group decisions concerning group members and establish linkages between
550 organizations. External recognition is also needed to influence others or become recognized as
551 an actor in the collective's environment. The lands of the CoC of Nhunggabarra had
552 geographical borders which every initiated adult had learned, and transgressions were

553 persecuted. Borders with non-CoC members were known by all initiated adults and trade posts
554 for friendly exchange were marked in rocks, still visible today. Similarly, STAP draws on the
555 principles of the international timebanking network and specific exchange platforms.

556 Contrary to the expectation in organization studies presented above, we do not believe external
557 recognition is a necessary goal; it can become crucial when the environment can sanction the
558 activity or threaten the existence of the organization. External institutions may impose
559 expectations of accountability (Laamanen et al., 2019; Segal and Lehrer, 2012). The
560 environment can thus claim the ability to legitimize or delegitimize a group making decisions.
561 Other situations illustrate the dependence on the environment, particularly when the
562 organization must connect with other organizations. Organizations may be subjected to
563 hierarchy willingly or otherwise while trying to avoid that outcome internally. The
564 Nhunggabarra and the other CoC members learned that in the hardest way possible in 1788
565 when the British military changed the environment from friendly horizontality to a hostile
566 hierarchy.

567 **Normalized horizontality**

568 The treatment of horizontality often departmentalizes it within dominant capitalist concepts of
569 organization and leadership. In this paper, we offer a synthesis of how the collective will is
570 operationalized in learning for citizen participants to relate horizontally to one another.
571 Horizontal practice is challenged by the ‘imperative’ of the active citizen or participant. The
572 problem recognized in the logic of collective action (Olson, 1965) is that the option of
573 freeriding deters participants from contributing. Formal organization can remove dependency
574 on the human resource and its (in)activity issues by allocating responsibilities and setting rules
575 (such as mandating participation in meetings or membership fees). However, Ostrom (1990)
576 suggested freeriding is less problematic in horizontal organizations than hierarchical

577 organizational discourse predicts. Freeriding is not necessarily resolved through the exercise
578 of collective will. While the higher values of horizontal organization indicate each member is
579 responsible for acting, in STAP, it is possible to freeride. Members can choose not to participate
580 in the maintenance of the organization, its decision-making and administrative tasks. In the
581 Nhunggal community this was solved by giving each member a set of responsibilities, some
582 from birth (totem animals), some resulting from a particular task or activity collective one
583 belonged to when coming of age (hunting, fishing, working the land, women's collective, etc.).
584 While these responsibilities are personal, the individuals' responsibilities interlink with others.
585 They must interact, participate in a sub-collective, and collaborate to complete tasks.
586 Consequently, the tasks require deliberation, socialization, and social control. This structure
587 seems rather effective against freeriding, especially when the higher order values of respect are
588 combined.

589 Where hierarchical organization is prone to polarization and in-/outgroup dynamics. The
590 horizontal organization in the Nhunggal case notably includes the membership of multiple sub-
591 collectives. This is central to preventing polarization and in-/outgroup dynamics. The
592 polarising *We-They* thinking is curtailed by belonging to multiple cross-cutting groups. The
593 situation also heads off conflict because each individual can view issues from multiple
594 perspectives.

595 In Nhunggal culture, things do not happen without a person's participation, thus their non-
596 participation would be noticed and have consequences, as everyone was expected to do their
597 part. In STAP, on the contrary, tasks are not allocated but are taken up voluntarily. This practice
598 places demands on those who accept responsibility but does not distribute responsibility
599 equally. This announced/clear responsibility for specific task areas is, however, important in
600 dealing with the tyranny of structurelessness (Freeman, 2013), creating the necessary
601 polycentric division of authority and active involvement by all to prevent the dynamic present

602 in the tyranny of structurelessness (Leach, 2013; Ostrom, 1990). Accordingly, we suggest
603 successful horizontal organization relies on clarity of the responsibility each member takes and
604 expecting all members to take some responsibility. That will require socializing new members
605 to accept responsibilities and teaching them how. With regard to socialization and learning,
606 while the Nhunggabarra case is a societal system covering the lifespan of its members, the
607 STAP case is a system that only deals with (the consumerist) part of the members' lives.

608 **Conclusion**

609 This article examined organizing the collective will. The concept of horizontal organization
610 questions the hierarchical definition of organization found in standard organization theory. The
611 concept of organization remains problematically hierarchical, even when a more horizontal
612 form is recognized (e.g. King et al., 2010). More broadly, we see manifestations of a collective
613 will in demands to resolve dire global problems that traditional hierarchical institutions seem
614 unwilling to address. Consequently, the demands are becoming louder, and people blame the
615 normalized hierarchical practices in traditional commercial organizations and political
616 institutions for the problems (Feola et al., 2021). The collective will legitimizes formal
617 organizations but also makes them accountable (DeHaven-Smith, 1998) and calls for informal
618 collaborations to find solutions (e.g. through the UN sustainable development goals; Melvin et
619 al., 2021). Accentuating collective will and normalized horizontality, we diverge from the
620 dominant narrative of organization involving an implicit or explicit hierarchy; instead, we
621 suggest that hierarchical conceptualization is not a prerequisite of organization, even as a
622 reference point.

623 **Notes**

624 ¹ The fourth, spiritual level is not covered in this article.

625 ² Laamanen et al. (2019) illustrate the frustrations between socialization and strategizing by
626 quoting a formerly active member saying that STAP “should have a long-term perspective on
627 thinking about [strategic questions] ... Then along comes the membership meeting, where we
628 spend an hour on [issues such as] logging in to the [online] platform, baking cakes for the next
629 meeting, and such”.

630 ³ Some older people with acknowledged wisdom could be addressed as “elder”. The informal
631 elders were an important knowledge source and no one would challenge their decisions.

632

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